

FEATURES OF WORD FORMATION.

Akhmedova Kamolaxhan

Research advisor: Muhayyo Umarova

Fergana State University

Abstract: The main purpose of writing this article is word formation and its thinking about types, methods of making. Today's word formation structure assess its completeness. Types and methods of word formation for students delivery, formation, growth, based on the required level of literacy ensure proper and reasonable use of Uzbek language opportunities issues are covered in this article.

Key words: word formation, word formation patterns, productive and ineffective patterns, artificial word, stemming, compound word.

Word formation is a separate branch of linguistics. It is the formation of words, its diachrony and deals with issues such as types of synchronicity, methods of word formation. Word production is a purely speech event, a speech process. However, it has a linguistic basis. That's it therefore, word formation is also related to language and speech. Word formation as a linguistic term, it has two meanings: the term of the word formation process and this the field that studies the process. Word formation is new in any way word formation is not understood. For example, as a result of a word acquiring a new meaning a new word may appear. Let's say that the word businessman has acquired a new meaning. However, there is no new word here. The phenomenon of word formation has been one of the current problems in linguistics and is still a controversial debate that has not lost its complexity. Word formation is the creation of new lexical units based on the possibilities and materials available in the language. The lexicon of the language is constantly enriched due to the factors of the change of dictionary meanings, the formation of words and the formation of new words. These factors, which interact with each other, serve to determine the development of the language. Their interrelationship is that new words in the language are associated with word acquisition, while word acquisition plays an important role in differentiating the meaning of lexical units. plays There is a need (possibility) to change meanings in cases

where the content of lexical units does not contradict the meaning of the emerging new word (or concept).

So word formation is artificial and new it is necessary to distinguish the phenomena of lexemization of words that have acquired meaning. Word the result of the development of the language is related to historicity and modernity. That's it

therefore, it is necessary to distinguish between historical and synchronous word formation. In the formation of the present word. There is a connection between the artificial word and the derivational pattern, the form and content of the template have left their traces in the derived word. The traces of the left (formative) and right (meaningful) side of the equal sign in the form of can be seen is standing. In the formation of a historical word, the form and meaning of the artificial word is a template will not be available. This is determined as a result of special inspections. For example, a village the meaning of the words of Avloq, their constituents and derivation patterns cannot be derived on the basis of Because they are historical creations. Guard, The same can be observed in the words yasovul and smooth. All kinds of word formation patterns based on Even if the product becomes linguistic and breaks from its mold, it is bindings to the known-unknown template (if the template is viable) are the same will be preserved.

The [English language](#) is known for its wonderful quality of the way in which words and sentences are formed and used. Formation of new words from an existing root word by adding a syllable or another word is the general process; however, there are multiple ways in which it can be done. The formation of words is classified into four types based on how the process of formation is carried out. They are:

- By adding prefixes
- By adding suffixes
- Converting from one word class to another
- Forming compound words

Let us look at each type of word formation in detail. Language users do this in three major ways. One way is to simply import a useful word from another language, just like people import useful products from other countries. This is how an Italian word like *pizza* or a Japanese word like *karaoke* became English words. Words that are circulated in this way among languages are called **borrowings**. Secondly, language users can change the meaning of words already in the language, to make them mean

different things. The English word *sad*, for example, is currently used to mean something similar to 'pathetic', besides keeping its meaning of 'unhappy'. In this new use, a *sad joke* is not a joke that makes you cry, but a joke that doesn't make you laugh. A third way of creating new words in a language involves manipulating not just their meaning but also their grammar, by disassembling the morphemes from the words in which they appear, and reassembling them into new words. This is what word formation is about.

It is known from history that the creation of a word seems to be simple and simple, but since its object and subject analysis is extremely complex, it is considered the most complex phenomenon in all fields except linguistics. The reason is that certain laws in it must be proven directly through the analysis of linguistic facts. For these reasons, scientists sometimes consider the phenomenon of word formation to belong to the field of morphology, and sometimes to the field of lexicology. In many scientific works, word formation is given as a part of grammar, while in other literature, it is applied as a part of lexicology. It seems that some of the artificial speech words exist only in the speech stage if so, some of them move away from the patterns that they have taken out and become linguistic as a whole "raised" to the level. Based on this, it can be said that lexemes can be original or artificial. For example, a book, a merchant, a baker let's take the units. Book and merchant units in a row are readiness, generality, has social properties. Although the lexeme of the merchant is artificial, it is a sign of readiness also has However, there is no linguistic unit called nonchi in our language. It is a lexeme of bread. Can be formed only in the speech process and has the above units without features. The peculiarity of the speech process of the bread unit is its readiness indicates that it does not have a symbol.

References:

1. Deterding, David H. and Poedjosoedarmo, Gloria R. (2001). Chapter 2. Morphology. In *The grammar of English. Morphology and syntax for English teachers in Southeast Asia*. Singapore: Prentice Hall, pp. 6-17.
2. Hudson, Grover (2000). Chapter 15. Six ways to get new words. In *Essential introductory linguistics*. Oxford: Blackwell, pp. 239-251.
3. Nurmonov A., Shahobiddinova Sh., Iskandarova Sh. and others. Object theoretical grammar of the language. Morphology. - Tashkent, "New Century Generation", 2001.-182 p.